

Carbon-Based Perovskite Solar Cell

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Abstract

In a short period, Perovskite solar cell (PSC) technology gained high efficiency and broad attention because of its key enabling physical and morphological features. One of the main obstacles to the PSC industrialization and commercialization deals with the demonstration of stable devices by adopting low-cost and reliable materials and fabrication methods. In the n-i-p structure, the organic hole-transporting layer and the metal counter-electrodes are the main causes of instability and high cost. Here, we substituted these two elements with a low-temperature and low-cost carbon-based counter electrode.

Keywords

perovskite solar cell; carbon; nanomaterial; low cost; hole transporting layer; stability; printing technique

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19 **1. Introduction**

20 The constant and unceasing progress of the technology in different areas requires renewable and green
21 energy sources [1]. The photovoltaic (PV) sector has a fundamental role to cover the energy demand. To
22 date, the PV market is based mainly on the "first generation" technology, i.e. monocrystalline and poly-
23 crystalline silicon, because of high conversion efficiency of solar radiation into electricity. Despite that,
24 the expensive manufacturing processes of silicon and its decreasing availability in nature have acceler-
25 ated the "second generation" thin-film technologies exploitation based on materials such as cadmium
26 telluride (CdTe) and amorphous silicon (a-Si) [2]. Besides this, The "third generation" PV aims to keep
27 high efficiency by reducing production costs thanks to hybrid-organic materials on rigid and flexible sub-
28 strates [3–6]. Natural dyes such as anthocyanins [7], polymers [8] or fullerenes [9] are just a few examples
29 of molecules used for this purpose. The main issue concerning these new technologies is the stability,
30 since the organic molecules used are very sensitive to the operating conditions, such as temperature, pro-
31 longed exposure to UV light, humidity. The materials toxicity of the materials used and the synthesis/pu-
32 rification costs are issues to be addressed.

33 In the recent years, Perovskite (PVSK) is widely used as photo-generator [10–12]. Its optical and elec-
34 tronic properties allowed a continuous development reaching record efficiencies (close to 26%) in a few
35 years [13]. PVSK is a chemical compound with ABX_3 formula, where A and B are cations with different
36 atomic radii and X represents an anion. Currently by PVSKs, we refer to all crystalline solids with the
37 same structure as $CaTiO_3$ (bipyramidal crystalline cell with square base). Recently perovskite-based ma-
38 terials organometallic compounds of halogens have gathered particular interest in PV field thanks to the
39 easy processability by solution together with efficiency comparable to the best inorganic materials used
40 in optoelectronics such as gallium arsenide (GaAs) and Si.

41 Typically, a PVSK solar cell (PSC) is a layered structure, where each layer performs a well-defined
42 function affecting the performance and the stability of the device. The PVSK is sandwiched between one
43 electron transport layer (ETL) and a hole transport layer (HTL). ETL and HTL are both connected to an
44 external circuit by gold or silver contacts. In case of n-i-p architecture, ETL is generally composed by c-
45 TiO_2 (compact TiO_2) and mp- TiO_2 (mesoporous TiO_2) or SnO_2 and guarantee good conduction, low charge
46 recombination and high transparency. The most widespread HTL is the 2,2',7,7'-Tetrakis(N,Ndi-p-meth-
47 oxyphenylamine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene. Spiro-MeOTAD ensures good energy levels of band gap, quick
48 charge transfer and low recombination, however there are still many related problems to the use of this

material, e.g. operational environment sensitivity, high cost (about 200 euro/g), complex synthesis and low yield [14]. Moreover, spiro-OMeTAD is doped to increase the mobility of the holes with highly hygroscopic salts (lithiumbis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (Li-TFSI) or 4-tert-butylpyridine (t-BP)) leading to PSC degradation deterioration. About the metal counter-electrode, gold diffuses into the structure of the device when exposed to continuous lighting, damaging it. It is possible to replace both the organic HTL and the metal electrode with one low temperature conductive carbon layer. Carbon materials are cheap if compared to HTMs (hole transporting materials) and gold, resulting in a reduction of cells cost and an increase in stability. Carbon is a key material widely used in the PV field due to its abundance, low cost, and appropriate energy level. Different kind of carbon materials [15–17], such as carbon nanotubes, carbon fiber, graphene have been applied with success in many PV devices. In the PVSCK field, the efficiencies are competitive with those measured in devices using spiro-OMeTAD as HTM [18–23]. Low temperature carbon pastes, unlike the porous high temperature inks [17,21], can be processed at temperatures below 130 °C exhibiting features of high conductivity, low cost, good stability and high throughput process.

In this paper, we demonstrate a simple process to fabricate HTL- and gold-free PSCs based on low temperature carbon counter-electrode by adopting solution-based processes for the full cell stack.

2. Materials and Methods

We adopted large area (1.01 cm²) n-i-p cells as reported in Figure 1a.

Figure 1. (a) PSC layers; (b) JV curves measurements; (c) Stability by MPP tracking.

We cleaned the FTO (fluorinated tin oxide) glasses (NSG, 8 Ω/sq.) in an ultrasonic system by using subsequent solvents (soap/water, acetone, ethanol and isopropanol) for 5 min each. We deposited 30 nm thick c-TiO₂ as reported in [24] and 250 nm thick mp-TiO₂ paste (Great Cell Solar 18 nrt, diluted with ethanol 1:4 *w/w*) is by spin coating method followed by 30 min@500 °C sintering in oven. The substrates are exposed to an UV lamp and then we deposited the triple cation PVSCK (C_{0.05}(MA_{0.17}FA_{0.83})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃) in DMF/DMSO, 1.42 M) (PbI₂ from TCI Co. Ltd.; CsI, FAI and MABr from Great Cell Solar) by spin-coating method in a glove-box. The spin-coating parameters to deposit the precursor solution are as follow: 1st step at 1000 rpm, 5 s ramping, 10 s; 2nd step 5000 rpm, 2s ramping, 30 s; chlorobenzene dropped 7 s before the end. Then, the PVSCK is annealed 60 min@100 °C. In a recent publication we demonstrated how to scale-up the triple cation PVSCK formulation to module device [24]. About the gold-based cells, Spiro-OMeTAD (Borum) HTM solution is prepared and deposited according to [14]. Following this, 85 nm-thick gold and 30 μm carbon (Dyename) counter-electrodes are thermally evaporated and blade-coated, respectively. The carbon-based cells are annealed at 60 °C in vacuum and 120 °C in air for 15 min in case of Spiro HTM and HTM-free, respectively. The JV curves and the stability measurements are reported by a Keithley source meter/LabVIEW under a class A sun simulator (Sun 2000, Abet) at AM 1.5 1000 W/m² calibrated by a Skye Instruments sensor Ltd.

3. Results and Discussion

The JV curves are depicted in Figure 1b and Table 1.

Table 1. Electrical parameters of the fabricated devices. HI is the Hysteresis Index [25].

Cell stack	Voc (V)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	HI
TiO ₂ /PVSK/Spiro/Carbon	0.90	12.67	39	4.40	1.20
TiO ₂ /PVSK/Carbon	1.01	19	53	10.20	1.05
TiO ₂ /PVSK/Spiro/Gold	1.02	20.30	65	13.40	1.25

In case of PVSK/Spiro/carbon cells all the electrical parameters are lower with respect to the PVSK/carbon cells. Most likely capacitive and recombination phenomena occur at Spiro/Carbon interface this inefficient set up affecting not only the fill factor, but also current and Voc. A lower FF mainly affects the PCE by comparing PVSK/carbon with PVSK/HTL/Gold cells, because of less conductivity of carbon electrode with respect to the gold one. It is also important to underline how the hysteresis phenomena are practically absent in the case of carbon-based cells by comparing the hysteresis index (HI) in Table 1 [26]. In case of PVSK/carbon cells, the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) is about 19 mA/cm², as reported in Figure 1b and Table 1. The best efficiencies are 13.4% and 10.2% for the PVSK/HTL/Gold and PVSK/Carbon devices, respectively (Figure 1b, Table 1). After 5 min in light condition at maximum power point the device loses just 4% efficiency and keeps stable at 9.8% (Figure 1c, Table 1).

4. Conclusion

The PV exploitation should avoid high-cost and high-CO₂ footprint materials and fabrication processes. The adoption of low-temperature carbon PSC counter-electrodes permits to avoid expensive organic HTM and metal counter-electrodes, such as gold or silver. These materials are also source of degradation leading to low stability in presence of moisture, temperature and light. Moreover, the carbon inks can be deposited by large area printing techniques, such as screen-printing and blade-coating. Since the carbon layer can be annealed at temperature less than 120 °C, the impact from the LCA (life cycle assessment) point of view is low. Here, we demonstrated how the PSCs can work without any HTL losing low efficiency. Further studies on low cost 2D PVSK strategies are in the pipeline to improve the electrical parameters of the cells. Moreover, the scaling up to module and stability assessment according to ISOS standard is ongoing.

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Data Availability Statement: Data supporting reported results are available in repository.

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References

- Eftekharijad, S.; Vittal, V.; Heydt, G.T.; Keel, B.; Loehr, J. Impact of increased penetration of photovoltaic generation on power systems. *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* **2013**, *28*, 893–901, doi:10.1109/TPWRS.2012.2216294.
- Barkhouse, D.A.R.; Gunawan, O.; Gokmen, T.; Todorov, T.K.; Mitzi, D.B. Yield predictions for photovoltaic power plants: empirical validation, recent advances and remaining uncertainties. *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.* **2015**, *20*, 6–11, doi:10.1002/pip.
- Mincuzzi, G.; Vesce, L.; Liberatore, M.; Reale, A.; Di Carlo, A.; Brown, T.M. Laser-sintered TiO₂ films for dye solar cell fabrication: An electrical, morphological, and electron lifetime investigation. *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices* **2011**, *58*, 3179–3188, doi:10.1109/TED.2011.2160643.
- Barichello, J.; Vesce, L.; Mariani, P.; Leonardi, E.; Braglia, R.; Di Carlo, A.; Canini, A.; Reale, A. Stable semi-

-
- 1 transparent dye-sensitized solar modules and panels for greenhouse application. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 6393,
2 doi:10.3390/en14196393.
- 3 5. Zardetto, V.; De Angelis, G.; Vesce, L.; Caratto, V.; Mazzuca, C.; Gasiorowski, J.; Reale, A.; Di Carlo, A.; Brown,
4 T.M. Formulations and processing of nanocrystalline TiO₂ films for the different requirements of plastic,
5 metal and glass dye solar cell applications. *Nanotechnology* **2013**, *24*, doi:10.1088/0957-4484/24/25/255401.
- 6 6. Dominici, L.; Vesce, L.; Colonna, D.; Michelotti, F.; Brown, T.M.; Reale, A.; Di Carlo, A. Angular and prism
7 coupling refractive enhancement in dye solar cells. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2010**, *96*, 1–3, doi:10.1063/1.3328097.
- 8 7. Yuvapragasam, A.; Muthukumarasamy, N.; Agilan, S.; Velauthapillai, D.; Senthil, T.S.; Sundaram, S. Natural
9 dye sensitized TiO₂ nanorods assembly of broccoli shape based solar cells. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B Biol.* **2015**,
10 *148*, 223–231, doi:10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2015.04.017.
- 11 8. Etxebarria, I.; Ajuria, J.; Pacios, R. Solution-processable polymeric solar cells: A review on materials, strategies
12 and cell architectures to overcome 10%. *Org. Electron.* **2015**, *19*, 34–60, doi:10.1016/j.orgel.2015.01.014.
- 13 9. Zhang, G.; Ning, H.; Chen, H.; Jiang, Q.; Jiang, J.; Han, P.; Dang, L.; Xu, M.; Shao, M.; He, F.; et al.
14 Naphthalenothiophene imide-based polymer exhibiting over 17% efficiency. *Joule* **2021**, *5*, 931–944,
15 doi:10.1016/j.joule.2021.02.003.
- 16 10. Kojima, A.; Teshima, K.; Shirai, Y.; Miyasaka, T. Organometal halide perovskites as visible-light sensitizers
17 for photovoltaic cells. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 6050–6051, doi:10.1021/ja809598r.
- 18 11. Snaith, H.J. Present status and future prospects of perovskite photovoltaics. *Nat. Mater.* **2018**, *17*, 372–376,
19 doi:10.1038/s41563-018-0071-z.
- 20 12. Feng, S.-P.; Cheng, Y.; Yip, H.-L.; Zhong, Y.; Fong, P.W.K.; Li, G.; Ng, A.; Chen, C.; Castriotta, L.A.; Matteocci,
21 F.; et al. Roadmap on Commercialization of Metal Halide Perovskite Photovoltaics. *J. Phys. Mater.* **2023**.
- 22 13. Green, M.A.; Dunlop, E.D.; Hohl-Ebinger, J.; Yoshita, M.; Kopidakis, N.; Bothe, K.; Hinken, D.; Rauer, M.;
23 Hao, X. Solar cell efficiency tables (Version 60). *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.* **2022**, *30*, 687–701,
24 doi:10.1002/pip.3595.
- 25 14. Vesce, L.; Stefanelli, M.; Di Carlo, A. Efficient and stable perovskite large area cells by low-cost fluorene-
26 xantene-based hole transporting layer. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 1–8, doi:10.3390/en14196081.
- 27 15. Calabrò, E.; Matteocci, F.; Paci, B.; Cinà, L.; Vesce, L.; Barichello, J.; Generosi, A.; Reale, A.; Di Carlo, A. Easy
28 Strategy to Enhance Thermal Stability of Planar PSCs by Perovskite Defect Passivation and Low-Temperature
29 Carbon-Based Electrode. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12*, 32536–32547, doi:10.1021/acsami.0c05878.
- 30 16. Barichello, J.; Vesce, L.; Matteocci, F.; Lamanna, E.; Di Carlo, A. The effect of water in Carbon-Perovskite Solar
31 Cells with optimized alumina spacer. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2019**, *197*, 76–83,
32 doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2019.03.029.
- 33 17. Vesce, L.; Riccitelli, R.; Mincuzzi, G.; Orabona, A.; Soscia, G.; Brown, T.M.; Di Carlo, A.; Reale, A. Fabrication
34 of spacer and catalytic layers in monolithic dye-sensitized solar cells. *IEEE J. Photovoltaics* **2013**, *3*, 1004–1011,
35 doi:10.1109/JPHOTOV.2013.2262374.
- 36 18. Stefanelli, M.; Vesce, L.; Di Carlo, A. Upscaling of Carbon-Based Perovskite Solar Module. *Nanomaterials* **2023**,
37 *13*, doi:10.3390/nano13020313.
- 38 19. Liu, Z.; Shi, T.; Tang, Z.; Sun, B.; Liao, G. Using a low-temperature carbon electrode for preparing hole-
39 conductor-free perovskite heterojunction solar cells under high relative humidity. *Nanoscale* **2016**, *8*, 7017–
40 7023, doi:10.1039/c5nr07091k.
- 41 20. Chu, Q.Q.; Ding, B.; Qiu, Q.; Liu, Y.; Li, C.X.; Li, C.J.; Yang, G.J.; Fang, B. Cost effective perovskite solar cells
42 with a high efficiency and open-circuit voltage based on a perovskite-friendly carbon electrode. *J. Mater.*
43 *Chem. A* **2018**, *6*, 8271–8279, doi:10.1039/c7ta10871k.
- 44 21. Dmitry Bogachuk, Salma Zouhair, Konrad Wojciechowski, Bowen Yang, Vivek Babu, L.W.; Bo Xu, Jaekeun

-
- 1 Lim, Simone Mastroianni, Henrik Pettersson, A.H. and A.H. Low-Temperature Carbon-based Electrodes in
2 Perovskite Solar Cells. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, doi:10.17226/21507.
- 3 22. Jiang, P.; Jones, T. W.; Duffy, N. W.; Anderson, K. F.; Bennett, R.; Grigore, M.; Marvig, P.; Xiong, Y.; Liu, T.;
4 Sheng, Y.. et al. No TitleFully printable perovskite solar cells with highly-conductive, lowtemperature,
5 perovskite-compatible carbon electrode. *Carbon N. Y.* **2018**, *129*, 830–836.
- 6 23. Lin, S.; Yang, B.; Qiu, X.; Yan, J.; Shi, J.; Yuan, Y.; Tan, W.; Liu, X.; Huang, H.; Gao, Y.; et al. Efficient and
7 stable planar hole-transport-material-free perovskite solar cells using low temperature processed SnO₂ as
8 electron transport material. *Org. Electron.* **2018**, *53*, 235–241, doi:10.1016/j.orgel.2017.12.002.
- 9 24. Vesce, L.; Stefanelli, M.; Herterich, J.P.; Castriotta, L.A.; Kohlstädt, M.; Würfel, U.; Di Carlo, A. Ambient Air
10 Blade-Coating Fabrication of Stable Triple-Cation Perovskite Solar Modules by Green Solvent Quenching.
11 *Sol. RRL* **2021**, *5*, 1–11, doi:10.1002/solr.202100073.
- 12 25. Chen, B.; Yang, M.; Priya, S.; Zhu, K. Origin of J-V Hysteresis in Perovskite Solar Cells. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*
13 **2016**, *7*, 905–917, doi:10.1021/acs.jpcclett.6b00215.
- 14 26. Ren, J.; Kan, Z. *Chapter 1: Origin of Hysteresis in Perovskite Solar Cells*; AIP Publishing LLC, 2020; Vol. 1; ISBN
15 9780735422414.
- 16 27. Vesce, L.; Guidobaldi, A.; Mariani, P.; Di Carlo, A.; Parisi, M.L.; Maranghi, S.; Basosi, R. Scaling-up of Dye
17 Sensitized Solar Modules. In *World Scientific Reference of Hybrid Materials*; 2019; Vol. 2, pp. 423–485.
18
19